

Figure 3-6 in “KnowPoetry: A Knowledge Service Platform for Tang Poetry Research based on Domain-Specific Knowledge Graph”

Figure 3: Data Requirement -- Data Theme

Figure 4: Data Requirement -- Data Source & Satisfaction

Figure 5: Data Requirement - Difficulties in Data Analysis

Figure 6: Function Requirement